

Synthesis, structure and photoluminescence properties of zinc(II)-naphthyl-(2-pyridylmethylene)amines and comparison with zinc(II)-naphthylazoimidazoles

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Abstract : Zinc(II) complexes of 1-alkyl-2-(naphthyl- α/β -azo)imidazoles (azoimine function, $-N=N-C=N-$) and α/β -naphthyl-(2-pyridylmethylene)amine (diimine function, $-N=C-C=N-$) are described in this article. The complexes are spectroscopically characterized (IR, UV-Vis, NMR). The composition of the complex depends on the counter ions used; the reaction of $ZnCl_2$ with ligand gives tetrahedral $Zn(\text{ligand})Cl_2$; $Zn(NO_3)_2$ prepares $-O-NO_2$ coordinated octahedral $[Zn(\text{ligand})_2(ONO_2)_2]$ compound while $Zn(ClO_4)_2$ isolates tetrahedral $[Zn(\text{ligand})_2](ClO_4)_2$ complex. Single crystal X-ray structure of $[Zn(\beta\text{-naphthyl-(2-pyridylmethylene)amine})_2(ONO_2)_2]$ has suggested coordination of $O-NO_2$ unit. Zinc(I)-diimine complexes are luminescent while zinc(II)-azoimine system are nonluminescent. Emission is of ligand centered $\pi-\pi^*$ origin and of good quantum yield (reference to coumarin-120).

Keywords : Zinc(II), naphthylamine Schiff base, naphthylazoimidazoles, crystal structure, luminescence.

The chemistry of bidentate nitrogen heterocyclic compounds containing 2,2'-bipyridine (bpy), 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) have been extensively studied¹⁻⁹ because of their spectroscopy, photophysics and photochemistry, redox properties, supramolecular chemistry etc. The functional group is diimine, $-N=C-C=N-$, and the key feature of these heterocycles is their π -acidity. Recent years have witnessed a great deal of interest in the synthesis of new ligands in the framework of diimine function ($-N=C-C=N-$). The number of hetero atoms, ring size and substituents in the heterocyclic ring significantly modify and regulate the physical and chemical properties of the compounds¹⁰. The modification may also be carried out by incorporating different pendent N-donor centres into N-heterocycle or using isoelectronic azoimine function ($-N=N-C=N-$). The condensation of pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde and $ArNH_2$ has synthesized bidentate chelating diimine function. However,

the ligands prepared from pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde and naphthylamines are scarce¹¹.

Naphthyl group is a sterically more crowded, electronically labile and more delocalised than phenyl group¹². Similarly, the azoimine function in 1-alkyl-2-(naphthyl-azo)imidazoles are reported by us in some cases¹³⁻¹⁶. In this article we wish to report zinc(II) complexes of 1-alkyl-2-(naphthyl- α/β -azo)imidazoles (α/β -NaiR) and α/β -naphthyl-(2-pyridylmethylene)amine (NaiPy) (Scheme 1). The complexes are characterized by different spectroscopic routes (IR, UV-Vis, NMR). The structural confirmation has been carried out in $Zn\{\beta\text{-naphthyl-(2-pyridylmethylene)-amine}\}_2(NO_3)_2$ by single crystal X-ray diffraction data. The Zn^{II} -diimine complexes are emitive while Zn^{II} -azo-imine are non-emitive.

Results and discussion

Two series of N,N'-functions are used in this work (Scheme 1) : azoimine ($-N=N-C=N-$) and diimine ($-N=C-C=N-$). 1-Alkyl-2-(naphthyl- α/β -azo)imidazoles (α -NaiR, 1 and β -NaiR, 2) are selected for azoimine system and α/β -naphthyl-(2-pyridylmethylene)amines (α -NaiPy, 3 and β -NaiPy, 4) are selected for diimine system.

The complexes were synthesized by reacting methanolic solution of ligand and $ZnCl_2$ in 1 : 1 mole ratio for and 2 : 1 mole proportion of ligand and $Zn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ or

α -NaiR (1) β -NaiR (2) α -NaiPy (3) β -NaiPy (4)

R = $-CH_3$ (a), $-CH_2-CH_3$ (b)

Scheme 1

Zn(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O (other molar ratios of ZnCl₂ : ligands such as 1 : 2 or 1 : 3 also separated complexes of composition identical to 1 : 1 mole ratio). Upon slow evaporation of reaction mixture orange crystals were deposited on the wall of beaker, which is separated by filtration and dried over CaCl₂. Microanalytical data support the composition, Zn(α/β-NaiR)Cl₂·H₂O (5, 6), [Zn((α/β-NaiR)₂)](NO₃)₂ (7, 8), [Zn(α/β-NaiR)₂](ClO₄)₂ (9, 10), Zn(α-NaiPy)Cl₂·H₂O (11), Zn(β-NaiPy)Cl₂·H₂O (12), Zn(α-NaiPy)₂(NO₃)₂ (13), Zn(β-NaiPy)₂(NO₃)₂ (14), Zn(α-NaiPy)₂(ClO₄)₂ (15), Zn(β-NaiPy)₂(ClO₄)₂ (16). Molar conductance data show that the compounds Zn(ligand)Cl₂ and Zn(ligand)₂(NO₃)₂ are non-conducting in nitromethane and suggest coordinated Cl⁻ and NO₃⁻ while the complexes Zn(ligand)₂(ClO₄)₂ show 1 : 2 conductivity. The NO₃⁻ may coordinate as chelating $\overline{M-O-N(O)-O}$ or monodentate M-O-NO₂ system. Infrared spectra of [Zn(ligand)₂](NO₃)₂ exhibit strong stretches at 1420, 1390, 1380 cm⁻¹, which are in support of coordinated Zn-O-NO₂ type bonding. The pseudooctahedral complexes of [Zn(ligand)₂(NO₃)₂] may exist in five different isomeric forms¹⁷. However, we have characterized only one isomer by single crystal X-ray diffraction study in which two -O-NO₂ groups present in *cis*-form and two chelating groups coordinated in such a fashion so that two heterocyclic-Ns (pyridine-N) appear in *trans*-form and two imine-N are in *cis*-form (Fig. 2). The complexes [Zn(ligand)₂](ClO₄)₂ show sharp single stretch at *ca.* 1090 and a weak stretch at 625 cm⁻¹ those are support of free ν(ClO₄)₄. Thus two chelating ligands orient in tetrahedral coordination form. The strong stretches at *ca.* 1610 cm⁻¹ in the complexes suggest the presence of ν(C=N) on comparing with reported data^{11a}. Other stretchings are also compared with free ligand spectra. Thermometric experiment has been carried out with 5, 6, 11, 12 and one mole of water is eliminated at 100–110 °C. This supports presence of H₂O in hydrogen bonded or coordinated form in the molecule. Infrared spectra show a broad medium intense stretch centred at *ca.* 3430 cm⁻¹ corresponding to ν(H₂O) which disappears on heating. Because of explosive -NO₃ and ClO₄⁻ we have not carried out thermal studies of other complexes.

(5, 6, 11, 12)

(7, 8, 13, 14)

(9, 10, 15, 16)

The electronic spectra of the Zn^{II}-naphthylazoimidazole complexes show absorption at 400–460 nm ($\epsilon \sim 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, Table 2) along with absorption in the UV region at *ca.* 350 nm and *ca.* 270 nm ($\epsilon \sim 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The band at visible region may be assigned to MLCT transition ($d^{10}(\text{Zn})$ to π^* state of azoimine function) while the transitions in UV region are due to intraligand charge transfer ($n-\pi^*$ and $\pi-\pi^*$) transitions. Zinc(II)-naphthyl-(2-pyridylmethylene)-amine complexes show MLCT band at 350–360 nm and intraligand two bands appear at 330–340 and 285–295 nm (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Absorption (left side) and emission (right side) spectra of Zn(α-NaiPy)₂(ClO₄)₂ in CHCl₃ at room temperature (298 K).

Table 1. Summarised crystallographic data for [Zn(β-NaiPy)₂(NO₃)₂] (14)

Empirical formula	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₆ Zn
Formula weight	653.96
Temperature (K)	293(2)
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	C2/c
Crystal size (mm) ³	0.40 × 0.20 × 0.20
Unit cell dimensions	
<i>a</i> (Å)	11.3820(7)
<i>b</i> (Å)	15.4910(7)
<i>c</i> (Å)	16.6460(15)
β (°)	96.440(6)
<i>V</i> (Å) ³	2916.5(3)
<i>Z</i>	8
λ (Å)	0.70930
μ (Mo-Kα) (mm ⁻¹)	0.901
<i>D</i> _{calcd} (g cm ⁻³)	1.489
Refine parameters	252
Reflection collected	8265
Unique data [<i>I</i> > 2σ (<i>I</i>)]	2396
<i>R</i> ₁ ^a [<i>I</i> > 2σ (<i>I</i>)]	0.0492
<i>wR</i> ₂ ^b	0.1389
Goodness of fit	1.072
^a <i>R</i> ₁ = Σ <i>F</i> _o - <i>F</i> _c / Σ <i>F</i> _o .	
^b <i>wR</i> ₂ = [Σ (<i>F</i> _o ² - <i>F</i> _c ²) / Σ <i>wF</i> _o ⁴] ^{1/2} , <i>w</i> = 1/[σ ² (<i>F</i> ²) + (0.0962 <i>P</i>) ² + (4.6158 <i>P</i>)]	

Table 2. UV-Vis^a and luminescence data in CH₃CN solution

Compd.	UV-Vis spectral data	λ_{abs}/nm	λ_{em}/nm (298 K)	λ_{em}/nm (77 K)	Quantum yield, ϕ
	λ_{max}/nm ($10^{-3}\epsilon, M^{-1} cm^{-1}$)				
[Zn(α -NaiMe)Cl ₂] (5a)	407(7.28), 334(4.85), 270(5.18)				
[Zn(β -NaiMe)Cl ₂] (6a)	440(4.41), 383(6.52), 287(3.58), 212(15.33)				
[Zn(α -NaiEt)Cl ₂] (5b)	402(1.126), 272(1.59), 212(8.27)				
[Zn(β -NaiEt)Cl ₂] (6b)	465(4.01), 348(2.68), 265(6.71)				
[Zn(α -NaiMe) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (7a)	445(4.25), 344(6.45), 265(6.85)				
[Zn(β -NaiMe) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (8a)	460(3.41), 342(4.51), 265(5.55)				
[Zn(α -NaiEt) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (7b)	448(4.53), 339(6.58), 270(7.38)				
[Zn(β -NaiEt) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (8b)	455(3.72), 340(3.22), 270(8.12)				
[Zn(α -NaiMe) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂ (9a)	452(5.70), 339(8.07), 272(7.43)				
[Zn(β -NaiMe) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂ (10a)	463(3.11), 349(2.11), 265(5.42)				
[Zn(α -NaiEt) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂ (9b)	469(4.43), 329(8.16), 272(7.198)				
[Zn(β -NaiEt) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂ (10b)	463(4.22), 348(3.17), 266(7.99)				
[Zn(α -NaiPy)Cl ₂] (11)	355(3.56) ^f , 335(4.98), 291(5.91)	335	437	470	0.0118
[Zn(β -NaiPy)Cl ₂] (12)	352(6.37) ^f , 330(7.07), 283(16.86)	336	414	438	0.0071
[Zn(α -NaiPy) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (13)	358(5.08) ^f , 332(8.82), 290(14.94)	330	422	465	0.0253
[Zn(β -NaiPy) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (14)	360(5.89) ^f , 334(14.80), 285(30.60)	334	431	465	0.0020
[Zn(α -NaiPy) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂ (15)	354(3.67) ^f , 334(5.58), 285(17.955)	334	441	472	0.0459
[Zn(β -NaiPy) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂ (16)	350(6.56) ^f , 334(15.90), 293(22.90)	334	458	483	0.0226

^aSolvent : CH₃CN; ^bquantum yields are expressed with reference to coumarin-120; ^cshoulder.

The ¹H NMR spectra are recorded in CDCl₃ solution. Data are given in Table 3. The assignment has been made on the basis of spin-spin interaction, and on comparing with 1-alkyl-2-(naphthyl- α/β -azo)imidazoles¹⁸ and pyridyl-2-(naphthylmethylene)amines^{11a,b}. All protons of the ligands suffer downfield shifting in the complexes compared to the free ligand values. In Zn- α/β -NaiR complexes imidazole protons, 4- and 5-H, are shifted by 0.05 to 0.25 ppm to higher δ which supports the coordination of imidazole-N to Zn^{II}. This conjecture has been proved by spectroscopic and single crystal X-ray structural studies of different Zn^{II}-azoimidazole complexes^{19,20}. Naphthyl protons appear as

multiplets except a broad singlet of 8-H and doublet of 10-H of Zn- β -NaiR complexes and a doublet of 15-H in case of all the zinc(II)-complexes. 1-Alkyl group appears as singlet to 1-Me in Zn- α/β -NaiMe and, quartet to -N-CH₂-, triplet to -CH₃ group in Zn- α/β -NaiEt complexes. Pyridyl-2-(naphthylmethylene)amines exhibit a singlet at most down field and has assigned to -HC=N- (7H) at 8.6–8.8 ppm. Other signals around 7.7–8.5 ppm refer to pyridine-H (3-H-6-H) and naphthyl signals appear in the upper field side, 7.2–7.6 ppm. Out of naphthyl and pyridyl protons the latter (3-H to 6-H) suffer are shifted to down field by 0.1–0.5 ppm from that of free ligand data^{11b}.

Molecular structure of [Zn(β -NaiPy)₂(NO₃)₂] (14) :

The crystal structure of [Zn(β -NaiPy)₂(ONO₂)₂] is shown in Fig. 2 and parameters are listed in Table 4. The structure shows a distorted octahedral geometry around Zn^{II}. The coordination sphere ZnN₄O₂ includes the coordination from two chelated ligands and two NO₃ groups bind through O centre. The ligand serves as diimine (-N=C-C=N-) donor function in which one N is pyridine-N and second one is exocyclic imine, -C=N-, group. A crystallographic 2-fold rotation axis is passed through Zn. Pseudooctahedral complexes may exist in five isomeric form²⁰. In this case arrangement shows two -O-NO₂ groups exist in *cis*-form; two pyridine-Ns appear in *trans*-

Fig. 2. Molecular structure of [Zn(β -NaiPy)₂(O-NO₂)₂] (14) (50% probability ellipsoids).

Table 3. ¹H NMR spectra[#] of the complexes in CDCl₃

Compd	δ, ppm (J, Hz)			6-H ^d	7-H ^c	8-H ^c	9-H ^d	10-H	11-H ^b	12,13-H ^b	14-H ^b	15-H ^d	-CH ₂ -	-CH ₃
	3-H ^a	4-H	5-H											
(5a)		7 28 ^d	6 88 ^d				8 72 (8 0)	7 80 ^b	7 80	7 51	7 44	7 94 (8 0)		4.01 ^c
(6a)		7 22 ^d	6 90 ^d			8 27		8 14 ^a (7 5)	8 00	7 55	7 45	7 40 (8 0)		4 08 ^c
(5b)		7 28 ^d	6 85 ^d				8 76 (8 0)	7 83 ^b	7 83	7 54	7 45	7 98 (8 0)	3 80 ^e (9 0)	0 86 ^f (7 5)
(6b)		7 23 ^d	6 90 ^d			8 22		8 10 ^a (7 5)	8 00	7 52	7 45	7 40 (8 0)	4 52 ^e (9 0)	1 05 ^f (7 5)
(7a)		7 28 ^d	6 82 ^d				8 48 (8 0)	7 75 ^b	7 75	7 52	7 42	7 92		3 94 ^c
(8a)		7 20 ^d	6 80 ^d			8 16		8 00 ^a (7 5)	7 96	7 45	7 38	7 30 (7 5)		
(7b)		7 15 ^d	6 82 ^d				8 52 (8 0)	7 72 ^b	7 50	7 50	7 41	7 90	3 80 ^e (9 0)	0 90 ^f (7 5)
(8b)		7 21 ^d	6 82 ^d			8 14		8 00 ^a (7 5)	7 92	7 42	7 35	7 30 (7 5)	4 42 ^e (9 0)	1 10 ^f (7 5)
(11)	7 97 (8 0)	7 86 ^f	7 86 ^f	8 55 (8 0)	8 83		7 63 (8 0)	7 57 ^b	7 49	7 49	7 49	7 25 (8 0)		
(12)	7 88 (8 0)	7 72 ^f	7 72 ^f	8 62 (8 0)	8 80	7 70		7 64 ^a (7 5)	7 48	7 44	7 44	7 21 (8 0)		
(13)	7 92 (8 0)	7 83 ^f	7 83 ^f	8 50 (8 0)	8 77		7 60 (8 0)	7 51 ^b	7 44	7 44	7 44	7 20 (8 0)		
(14)	7 85 (8 0)	7 68 ^f	7 68 ^f	8 63 (8 0)	8 77	7 72		7 60 ^a (7 5)	7 42	7 42	7 42	7 26 (8 0)		
(15)	7 83 (8 0)	7 77 ^f	7 77 ^f	8 45 (8 0)	8 55		7 57 (8 0)	7 50 ^b	7 43	7 43	7 43	7 20 (8 0)		
(16)	7 80 (8 0)	7 70 ^f	7 70 ^f	8 52 (8 0)	8 70	7 70		7 62 ^a (7 5)	7 40	7 40	7 40	7 22 (8 0)		

[#]The complexes [Zn(NaIR)₂](ClO₄)₂ (9, 10) are not sufficiently soluble in CDCl₃ to run NMR spectra

^aDoublet, ^bmultiplet, ^csinglet, ^dbroad singlet, ^equartet, ^ftriplet

form and two imine-Ns are oriented in *cis*-configuration. Two atomic groups Zn(1), N(3), N(2), O(1), N(2₂) (plane 1) and Zn(1), N(2), O(1₂), N(2₂), N(3₂) (plane 2) constitute

Fig. 3. 3-D packing view showing hydrogen bonds and π-π interactions

excellent plane (maximum deviation 0.02 Å). The atomic group Zn(1), N(3), N(3₂), O(1), O(1₂) (plane 3) constitute also a plane. Plane 1 and 2 makes an angle 87.98° and plane 3 makes an angle 88.38° with plane 1 (plane 2). Two chelate planes constituting from set of atoms Zn(1), N(3), C(16), C(5₂), N(2₂) and Zn, N(2), C(5), C(16₂), N(3₂) makes a dihedral 71.35°. The chelate angle is [N(3)-Zn-N(2₂)/N(2)-Zn(1)-N(3₂)] 75.57(11)° and is deviated from regular pentagonal angle. This may cause distortion to the octahedral geometry. The angle O(1)-Zn(1)-N(2₂)/N(1₂)-Zn(1)-N(3₂), 157.58(10) and N(2)-Zn(1)-N(2₂), 167.09(16)° are reduced from the *trans* angular values may be due to acute chelate bite angle. The imine -C=N- distance is 1.271(5) Å; the Zn-N(pyridine) [Zn(1)-N(2)/Zn(1)-N(2₂)] and Zn-N(naph) [Zn(1)-N(3)/Zn(1)-N(3₂)] bond distances are not equivalent, 2.114(3) and 2.291(3) Å respectively. This indicates a better interaction with Zn with pyridine-N than imine-N. Intermolecular hydrogen bond is observed between imine (-N=C)-H of one molecule and

O(NO₂) of neighbouring molecule [C(16)-H(16)---O(3)-NO₂ : C(16)-H(16), 0.94 Å; H(16)---O(3), 2.59(3) Å; C(16)---O(3), 3.326(4) Å; ∠(C-H-O), 136(2)°. Symmetry : 1/2+x, 1/2+y, z). This hydrogen bonding interaction leads to the formation of 1-D chain. Naphthyl groups exhibit π-π interaction (distance, 4.045(8) Å and dihedral angle, 1.40°, symmetry : 3/2 -x; 3/2 -y; 2 - z) which leads to the formation of 3-D supramolecular geometry (Fig. 3).

Photoluminescence properties :

The photoluminescence properties of the ligands and complexes were studied at room temperature (298 K) and 77 K (Fig. 1) in CHCl₃. Data are collected in Table 2. The Schiff bases exhibit photoluminescence with emission at 431 and 406 nm for α-NaiPy and β-NaiPy respectively at 298 K upon excitation at 330 nm. Under low temperature (77 K) these compounds show emission at 455 nm for α-NaiPy and 448 nm for β-NaiPy^{11a,b}.

Table 4. Selected bond length (Å) and bond angles (°)

	Bond length (Å)	Bond angle (°)
Zn(1)-N(2)	2.114(3)	N(2)-Zn(1)-N(3) 75.57(11)
Zn(1)-N(3)	2.291(3)	N(1)-O(1)-Zn(1) 121.69(4)
Zn(1)-O(1)	2.090(3)	Zn(1)-N(2)-C(5) 116.31(2)
N(3)-C(16)	1.271(5)	Zn(1)-N(3)-C(16) 110.97(16)
N(1)-O(1)	1.279(4)	O(2)-N(1)-O(1) 119.95(5)
N(1)-O(2)	1.226(5)	O(2)-N(1)-O(3) 120.77(6)
N(1)-O(3)	1.213(5)	O(1)-N(1)-O(3) 119.28(2)
		O(1)-Zn(1)-N(2) 97.94(11)
		O(1)-Zn(1)-N(3) 157.58(10)

No emission originating from metal-centred and MLCT or LMCT excited states are expected for the Zn^{II} complexes, since the Zn^{II} ion is difficult to oxidize or reduce due to its *d*¹⁰ configuration. Thus, the emission observed in the complexes is tentatively assigned to the (π-π*) intraligand fluorescence. It is interesting that the Zn^{II} complexes show higher intensity than that of the free ligand value. It has been reported that the metal ions can enhance or quench the fluorescence emission of pyridine containing compounds²¹. In the absence of metal ions the fluorescence of ligand is probably quenched by the occurrence of a photoinduced electron transfer (PET) process due to the presence of a lone pair of nitrogen atoms. Such a PET process is prevented by the complexation of ligand with metal ions; thus the fluorescence intensity may be greatly enhanced by the coordination to Zn^{II}. The chelation of the ligands increases rigidity and reduces the loss of energy by thermal vibrational decay. At low temperature (77 K) the complexes show bright greenish-blue emission and have been red shifted by 30–40 nm from the emission in solution at 298 K. This is probably caused by intermolecular interac-

tions in the freezed condition that effectively decreases the energy gap. Quantum yields are estimated with reference to coumarine-120 (Table 2) and it is observed that Zn^{II}-α-NaiPy complexes are better fluorophore than Zn^{II}-β-NaiPy complexes.

Conclusion :

Zinc(II) complexes of 1-alkyl-2-(naphthyl-α/β-azo)imidazoles (azoimine function, -N=N-C=N-) and α/β-naphthyl-2-(2-pyridylmethylene)amine (diimine function, -N=C-C=N-) are characterized by elemental analyses and spectroscopic data. Use of ZnCl₂ has synthesized monochelated Zn(N,N')Cl₂ complexes while Zn(NO₃)₂ and Zn(ClO₄)₂ prepare Zn(N,N')₂(X)₂ (X = NO₃⁻ and ClO₄⁻) complexes. Nitrate (NO₃⁻) serves as monodentate donor and has been established by single crystal X-ray structure of Zn(β-naphthyl-2-pyridylmethylene)amine)₂(ONO₂)₂. The Zn^{II}-diimine complexes exhibit luminescence property while Zn^{II}-azoimine complexes are silent.

Experimental

Materials and measurements :

α-Naphthylamine and β-naphthylamine were purchased from Thomas Baker & Co. Pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde was purchased from Lancaster Ltd., England. Pyridyl-2-(α/β-naphthylmethylene)amine were synthesized by equimolar condensation of pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde and naphthylamine in ethanol following previously reported procedure¹¹. 1-Alkyl-2-(naphthyl-α/β-azo)imidazoles (α/β-NaiR) are synthesized by reported procedure¹³. All other chemicals used were of A.R. quality and used as received.

UV-Vis spectra were recorded using Perkin-Elmer Lambda 25 spectrophotometer and infrared spectra were obtained from Perkin-Elmer RX-1 FT-IR instrument. Microanalyses were collected from Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHN elemental analyser. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded from Bruker 300 MHz FT-NMR. Solution electrical conductivity was measured in Systronics 305 digital conductivity meter. Thermogravimetric experiments have been carried out using DT/TG 50 thermal analyzer under air.

The fluorescence quantum yield of the Schiff bases (NaiPy) and their zinc(II) complexes was determined using Coumarine-120 laser dye as a reference with a known φ_R of 0.63 in MeCN. The complex and the reference dye were excited at 333 ± 3 nm, maintaining nearly equal absorbance (~0.1), and the emission spectra were recorded from 350 to 600 nm. The area of the emission spectrum was integrated using the software available in the instrument and the quantum yield is calculated according to the following equation :

$$\phi_S/\phi_R = [A_S/A_R] \times [(Abs)_R/(Abs)_S] \times [\eta_S^2/\eta_R^2]$$

Here, ϕ_S and ϕ_R are the fluorescence quantum yield of the sample and reference, respectively. A_S and A_R are the area under the fluorescence spectra of the sample and the reference respectively, $(Abs)_S$ and $(Abs)_R$ are the respective optical densities of the sample and the reference solution at the wavelength of excitation, and η_S and η_R are the values of refractive index for the respective solvent used for the sample and reference.

Preparation of the complexes :

Synthesis of [Zn(1-methyl-2-(naphthyl- α -azo)imidazole- Cl_2) $_2$] monohydrate, [Zn(α -NaiEt) Cl_2] $_2$.H $_2$ O (5a) :

1-Methyl-2-(naphthyl- α -azo)imidazole (0.25 g, 1.06 mmol) in MeOH (10 cc) was added dropwise to a methanolic solution (10 cc) of ZnCl $_2$ (0.16 g, 1.17 mmol) at room temperature and stirred for 1 h. The solution was then filtered and kept undisturbed for a week. Orange crystals appear on the wall of beaker. The bright crystalline product was then recrystallised by diffusion of CH $_2$ Cl $_2$ solution into hexane. The yield was 0.25 g, 61%.

Other compounds were prepared following identical procedure and isolated in the yield of 54–65%. Microanalytical data are as follows : Anal. Calcd. for Zn(α -NaiMe) Cl_2 .H $_2$ O (5a), C $_{14}$ H $_{14}$ N $_4$ ZnCl $_2$ O : C, 43.04; H, 3.59; N, 14.35. Found : C, 43.11; H, 3.52; N, 14.47%. Zn(α -NaiEt) Cl_2 .H $_2$ O (5b), C $_{15}$ H $_{16}$ N $_4$ ZnCl $_2$ O : C, 44.52; H, 3.96; N, 13.85. Found : C, 44.43; H, 4.03; N, 13.77%. Zn(β -NaiMe) Cl_2 .H $_2$ O (6a), C $_{14}$ H $_{14}$ N $_4$ ZnCl $_2$ O : C, 43.04; H, 3.59; N, 14.35. Found C, 43.00; H, 3.54; N, 14.42%. Zn(β -NaiEt) Cl_2 (6b), C $_{15}$ H $_{16}$ N $_4$ ZnCl $_2$ O : C, 44.52; H, 3.96; N, 13.85. Found : C, 44.60; H, 4.05; N, 13.73%. Zn(α -NaiMe) $_2$ (NO $_3$) $_2$ (9a), C $_{28}$ H $_{24}$ N $_{10}$ O $_6$ Zn : C, 50.81; H, 3.63; N, 21.17. Found : C, 50.77; H, 3.60; N, 21.25%. Zn(α -NaiEt) $_2$ (NO $_3$) $_2$ (9b), C $_{30}$ H $_{28}$ N $_{10}$ O $_6$ Zn : C, 52.22; H, 4.06; N, 20.31. Found : C, 52.29; H, 4.02; N, 20.42%. Zn(β -NaiMe) $_2$ (NO $_3$) $_2$ (10a), C $_{28}$ H $_{24}$ N $_{10}$ O $_6$ Zn : C, 50.81; H, 3.63; N, 21.17. Found : C, 50.85; H, 3.67; N, 21.23%. Zn(β -NaiEt) $_2$ (NO $_3$) $_2$ (10b), C $_{30}$ H $_{28}$ N $_{10}$ O $_6$ Zn : C, 52.22; H, 4.06; N, 20.31. Found : C, 52.16; H, 4.08; N, 20.40%. Zn(α -NaiMe) $_2$ (ClO $_4$) $_2$ (13a), C $_{28}$ H $_{24}$ N $_8$ O $_8$ Cl $_2$ Zn : C, 45.63; H, 3.26; N, 15.21. Found : C, 45.56; H, 3.33; N, 15.30%. Zn(α -NaiEt) $_2$ (ClO $_4$) $_2$ (13b), C $_{30}$ H $_{28}$ N $_8$ O $_8$ Cl $_2$ Zn : C, 47.10; H, 3.66; N, 14.65. Found : C, 47.17; H, 3.62; N, 14.71%. Zn(β -NaiMe) $_2$ (ClO $_4$) $_2$ (14a), C $_{28}$ H $_{24}$ N $_8$ O $_8$ Cl $_2$ Zn : C, 45.63; H, 3.26; N, 15.21. Found : C, 45.67; H, 3.30; N, 15.27%. Zn(β -NaiEt) $_2$ (ClO $_4$) $_2$ (14b), C $_{30}$ H $_{28}$ N $_8$ O $_8$ Cl $_2$ Zn : C, 47.10; H, 3.66; N, 14.65. Found : C, 47.06; H, 3.62; N, 14.58%.

Synthesis of di-chloro-(α -naphthyl-(2-pyridylmethylene)amine)zinc(II) monohydrate, Zn(α -NaiPy) Cl_2 .H $_2$ O (7) :

α -Naphthyl-(2-pyridylmethylene)amine (0.25 g, 1.08 mmol) in MeOH (10 cc) was added dropwise to a methanolic solution (10 cc) of ZnCl $_2$ (0.16 g, 1.17 mmol) at room temperature and stirred for 3 h. The solution colour turned yellow. The volume is reduced to half of its original volume by slow evaporation in air. Yellow crystals then separated. It was filtered, washed with water, water-MeOH (1 : 1, v/v). The product was then crystallized by diffusion of CH $_2$ Cl $_2$ solution into hexane. The yield was 0.28 g (74%). Anal. Calcd. for C $_{16}$ H $_{12}$ N $_2$ Cl $_2$ OZn (7), C, 49.70; H, 3.62; N, 7.25. Found : C, 49.82; H, 3.58; N, 7.33%. [Zn(β -naphthyl-(2-pyridylmethylene)amine) Cl_2] was prepared similarly by 68% yield. Anal. Calcd. for C $_{16}$ H $_{12}$ N $_2$ Cl $_2$ OZn (8), C, 49.70; H, 3.62; N, 7.25. Found : C, 49.65; H, 3.60; N, 7.18%.

Synthesis of [Zn(α -naphthyl-(2-pyridylmethylene)amine) $_2$ (NO $_3$) $_2$], [Zn(α -NaiPy) $_2$ (NO $_3$) $_2$] (11) :

α -Naphthyl-(2-pyridylmethylene)amine (0.25 g, 1.08 mmol) in MeOH (10 cc) was added dropwise to a methanolic solution (10 cc) of Zn(NO $_3$) $_2$.6H $_2$ O (0.16 g, 0.54 mmol) at room temperature and stirred for 3 h. The volume of yellow solution is reduced to half of its original volume by slow evaporation in air. The solution was then kept in refrigerator maintaining temperature at 5 °C. The bright yellow crystalline product was then recrystallised from MeOH-H $_2$ O (1 : 1, v/v) and dried over CaCl $_2$. The yield was 0.22 g, 64%. Anal. Calcd. for C $_{32}$ H $_{24}$ N $_6$ O $_6$ Zn (11), C, 58.78; H, 3.67; N, 12.68. Found : C, 58.65; H, 3.62; N, 12.79%. [Zn(β -naphthyl-(2-pyridylmethylene)amine) $_2$ (NO $_3$) $_2$] was prepared similarly and the yield was 70%. Anal. Calcd. for C $_{32}$ H $_{24}$ N $_6$ O $_6$ Zn (12), C, 58.78; H, 3.67; N, 12.68. Found : C, 58.64; H, 3.63; N, 12.80%.

Synthesis of bis-(α -naphthyl-(2-pyridylmethylene)amine)zinc(II) perchlorate, [Zn(α -NaiPy) $_2$](ClO $_4$) $_2$ (15) :

α -Naphthyl-(2-pyridylmethylene)amine (0.25 g, 1.08 mmol) in MeOH (10 cc) was added dropwise to a methanolic solution (10 cc) of Zn(ClO $_4$) $_2$.6H $_2$ O (0.2 g, 0.54 mmol) at room temperature and stirred for 3 h. The volume of solution was reduced to half of its original volume by slow evaporation in air. The solution was then kept in refrigerator maintaining temperature at 5 °C. The bright yellow crystalline product was then recrystallised from MeOH-H $_2$ O (1 : 1, v/v) and dried over CaCl $_2$. The yield was 0.24 g, 61%. Anal. Calcd. for C $_{32}$ H $_{24}$ N $_4$ O $_8$ Cl $_2$ Zn (15), C, 52.73; H, 3.30; N, 7.69. Found : C, 52.65; H, 3.22; N, 7.79%. [Zn(β -naphthyl-(2-pyridylmethylene)amine) $_2$ (ClO $_4$) $_2$] was prepared similarly (60%). Anal. Calcd. for C $_{32}$ H $_{24}$ N $_4$ O $_8$ Cl $_2$ Zn

(16), C, 52.73; H, 3.30; N, 7.69. Found : C, 52.77; H, 3.28; N, 7.74%.

Crystallographic data collection and refinement of [Zn(β-NaiPy)₂(ONO₂)₂] (14) :

Crystals were grown (0.40 × 0.20 × 0.20 mm³) by slow evaporation of methanol solution of the reaction mixture of Zn(NO₃)₂ and β-NaiPy in 1 : 1 molar proportion. Crystal parameters and refined data are summarized in Table 1. The data were collected by Enraf-Nonius CAD-4 diffractometer at 293(2) K using graphite-monochromatized Mo-Kα radiation (λ = 0.70930 Å). Unit cell parameters were determined from least-squares refinement of setting angles with 2θ in the range 4.46 ≤ 2θ ≤ 49.84°. Total data collected are 8265 out of which unique data are 2396. The *hkl* range are 0 ≤ *h* ≤ 13, 0 ≤ *k* ≤ 18, -9 ≤ *l* ≤ 19. Reflection data were recorded using the ω scan technique. Data collection and refinement were done by using Argus MACH3 Nonius software. Data were corrected for Lorentz polarization effects and for linear decay. Semi-empirical absorption corrections based on Ψ-scans were applied. The structure was solved by direct method using SHELXS-97 and successive difference Fourier syntheses. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. The hydrogen atoms were fixed geometrically and refined using the riding model. In the final difference Fourier map the residual minima and maxima, -0.641 and 0.619 e/Å³, were carried out using SHELXL-97. All calculations were carried out using SHELXL-97²², ORTEP-3²³, PLATON-99²⁴ programs.

Supplementary data :

Crystallographic data for the structural analysis are in the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, and CCDC No. 289370 [Zn(β-NaiPy)₂(ONO₂)₂]. Copies of this information may be obtained free of charge from the Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge, CB2 1FZ, UK (*E-mail* : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk>).

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